

ENERGY SYSTEMS
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CCG POLICY BRIEF

Economic Data Gaps & Challenges for Energy Systems Modelling: Hydroelectric Power

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Summary

Hydroelectric power currently provides the largest share of renewable electricity globally, generating more electricity than all other renewable technologies combined. Whilst its contributions to the global electricity supply are expected to be overtaken by other renewables such as wind and solar, it will likely continue to play a key role in providing low-carbon, dispatchable electricity in countries with the local geography to deploy hydroelectric power. For these countries, the formulation of their strategy and deployment plans for hydroelectric power relies on technical insights gained from energy system models (ESMs) and individual resource assessments. However, the deployment scenarios for hydroelectric power are sensitive to its relative costs against other low-carbon technologies. The costs of electricity generated from hydroelectric power vary substantially both within and between countries, posing challenges in making accurate assumptions in countries with limited deployment. Here, we discuss how global ranges taken from the open literature could be used to define and justify assumptions regarding the cost of hydroelectric power by stakeholders struggling to access country-specific empirical data.

Key Policy Recommendations

- Hydroelectric power holds strong potential to deliver low-carbon electricity in countries with suitable geographies, and its use should be explored when developing national energy and climate strategies.
- For these countries, the sensitivity of ESMs and individual project assessments regarding the assumed costs of hydroelectric power needs to be accounted for when used to provide technical and policy insights.
- Researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders operating in countries which lack empirical data should conduct scoping studies to understand its costs, using global cost ranges from the literature to situate cost assumptions for ESMs when this is not possible.

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Economic Data Gaps & Challenges for Energy Systems Modelling of Hydroelectric Power

Introduction

Hydroelectric power is expected to remain the world's largest source of renewable electricity generation into the 2030s, providing a source of low-carbon, dispatchable power that does not suffer from intermittency issues like other renewables, such as wind or solar power. The International Energy Agency predicts in its Net Zero Scenario that the installed capacity globally could increase by over 25% to 1,765 GW in 2030 from an existing 1,393 GW in 2022 [1]. As a highly mature technology that could also offer a way to smooth out variations in generation from solar and wind through pumped hydro storage, hydropower is well equipped to play a critical role in the future decarbonised electricity system.

Despite its role as the largest renewable generation technology by electricity production, there is still substantial uncertainty over the future costs of electricity from hydroelectric power, especially in countries without any empirical data and/or prior deployment. The costs of hydroelectric power are also heavily affected by design choices and the local geography of deployment [2], meaning that even within countries the costs of deployment can vary substantially between different sites. The total installed costs for hydroelectric power reported by IRENA for between 2016–2022 varied from a low of USD 800/kW to a high of over USD 5,000/kW [3], a ratio of over 5x, highlighting the care needed when drawing cost assumptions from empirical data for the deployment of new hydroelectric power.

Whilst existing research has examined the global technical and economic potential for hydroelectric power [4] and its role in the decarbonisation of individual country's electricity grids [5], [6], there are few studies that compare the global range of costs associated with its deployment. This policy brief outlines a curated dataset that presents global ranges of the technoeconomic parameters (eg capital costs, operating costs) which are key to modelling the cost of hydroelectric power, drawn from the open and grey literature. The aim of this brief is to discuss the challenges around data availability for hydroelectric power, especially in the Global South, and highlight the wide range of costs for hydroelectric power influenced by local geographies. This brief also aims to provide data for energy system modellers and other stakeholders that can situate and justify their cost assumptions, which may be used to develop strategies for hydroelectric power deployment and inform energy and climate commitments.

Drawing upon the existing literature base

Technoeconomic data on hydroelectric power were gathered to inform the assumptions used in large-scale energy systems modelling tools such as the OSeMOSYS [7]. Relevant data were collected from websites, reports, academic articles, and databases of national and international organisations. The data covers the range of parameters needed for the technoeconomic analysis of hydroelectric power, including operating costs, capital costs, construction times and total operational lifetime. The dataset has been made openly accessible in the Zenodo Data Repository and can be accessed via the following link:

<https://zenodo.org/records/10884068>. The dataset shared on the Zenodo link contains the sources that were used to populate the database.

Global current capital costs for hydroelectric power

Error! Reference source not found. shows the range of overnight capital costs for the deployment of hydroelectric power, taken across 2020–2024. The costs extracted from the open literature between 2020–2024 show substantial variation, with a median value of 4,491 and 8,057 USD/kW for reservoir and run of river (RoR) based hydroelectric power. Data that were found in the open literature covered the major regions and economies of the world, where geographically appropriate, with the large ranges highlighting the location and geographic specificity of the costs of deploying hydroelectric power.

Figure 1: Range of a) capital costs and b) fixed operating costs for hydroelectric power stations in 2020–2024, for reservoir and run-of-river (RoR) and stated in 2023 US dollar terms. The lower and upper bounds of each shaded box represent the lower and upper quartile of the data (25th and 75th percentile respectively), with the central line representing the median. Whiskers represent the range of values falling within 1.5 times the inter-quartile range, and outliers are shown with diamonds. The 25th, 50th, and 75th percentile values are written to the left of each bar.

Using global ranges to address empirical data gaps

Hydroelectric power will continue to play a key role in the supply of low-carbon electricity globally, with many scenarios predicting that it will be the dominant source of low-carbon electricity over the next decade globally [1]. Understanding the current and future costs of deployment will be key to the effective design of policy support and the development of appropriate integrated energy and climate strategies. Error! Reference source not found. shows the range of capital costs between 2020–2024 by region (where available), and projected global costs in 2030 and 2050. Some countries and regions across the globe have limited or non-existent deployment of hydroelectric power, causing data availability issues for techno-economic parameters such as installation or financing costs that are key to competitiveness of electricity from hydroelectric power. These data gaps create significant difficulties for energy system modellers around the justification of cost assumptions for hydroelectric power and could affect the creation of deployment strategies for hydroelectric power in some countries.

Figure 2: Range of capital costs for hydroelectric power stations in a) 2020–2024 for each world region, where available, and b) global projections for 2030 and 2050. Costs are stated in 2023 US dollar terms.

In countries and regions with limited empirical data on hydroelectric power, it is important for energy system modellers and other stakeholders to clearly highlight the cost assumptions used in power and energy system modelling. Decarbonisation pathways and technical insights developed from modelling will likely be highly sensitive to the costs of hydropower. Transparent documentation of assumptions and methodologies will also increase confidence in the modelling results, facilitating informed decision-making by policymakers and other stakeholders. The ranges presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** are intended to serve as a useful tool to situate assumptions in energy system models (ESMs) for these countries against empirical data taken from other countries and regions, addressing the data gaps whilst still providing robust technical insights to support the development of energy and climate strategies by policymakers.

Prioritising transparency and data sharing amongst stakeholders will also be essential to enhance the accuracy and utility of ESMs. By openly sharing data and methodologies, academic researchers, government ministries, industry professionals, and other stakeholders can work collaboratively to address data gaps, compare and contrast their assumptions, and so improve the reliability of energy system modelling outcomes. Given the potential sensitivity of ESMs and assessments of hydroelectric potential to the assumed capital and operating costs of hydroelectric power, energy system modellers should also conduct sensitivity tests to assess the robustness of their models. Understanding how variations in cost assumptions impact model outcomes will be crucial for making informed decisions and developing resilient energy transition pathways, and situating their assumptions against the global cost curve could be a useful way of exploring model sensitivities.

However, whilst the global ranges from the open literature presented in this work can provide valuable insights and offer a way to address empirical data gaps, they should complement, not replace, direct engagement with private sector stakeholders. Collaborating with industry partners can enrich data collection efforts and ensure that ESMs accurately reflect real-world conditions and the true costs of hydroelectric power.

Conclusions

Addressing the challenges of data availability for hydroelectric power will be critical to accelerating the energy transition in countries with suitable geographies, particularly in countries in the Global South where there are limited empirical data. Recognising the sensitivity of ESMs and resource assessments to the capital and operating costs of hydroelectric power can help stakeholders to enhance the accuracy and reliability of technical insights. Accurate data can support the development of integrated energy and climate strategies, enabling rapid grid decarbonisation. Whilst global ranges from the open literature can serve as useful reference points, engaging with private sector stakeholders will be essential for understanding and capturing the complexities of real-world deployment scenarios.

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Author Statement

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